

LARGE SCALE SLAMMING TESTS ON COMPOSITE BUOYS FOR WAVE ENERGY APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

In the European project SEEWEC, a design for a wave energy converter is studied. Floating point absorbers, made in filament wound composite, pick up the wave energy. The survivability in storm conditions is most critical. Large scale slamming tests have been performed to assess the peak pressures, decelerations and deformations during impact.

Keywords: slamming, wave energy converter, fluid-structure interaction, filament winding, wave impact

INTRODUCTION

Seewec

The European FP6 project SEEWEC was started to investigate the feasibility of a new design of wave energy converter (WEC) by Fred Olsen Ltd. The WEC consists of a floating offshore-like platform with 21 floating point absorbers attached to it as is shown in Figure 1. The floaters move up and down along a guiding rod in the waves. By damping these motions electricity is produced. This might be realised by means of a hydraulic intermediate stage and a generator or directly with a linear generator. The design of the platform is based on platforms for gas exploitation. It is important for the sustainability and the structural strength of the total device since, as for each kind of energy conversion system, there is opted for maximum efficiency. Additionally, offshore wind and WEC's have to survive storms of a predefined level. Hence, both efficiency and structural strength are important and for this the platform is very good. Next, the Seewec structure is designed to stay the whole year long at sea. However, in

extreme conditions called the Ultimate Limit State (ULS), it should not operate anymore.

Figure 1 Concept of the Seewec design.

Background

The general concept of the device was launched, as mentioned, by Fred Olsen Ltd. in 2001. Next, the first steps in the development were taken at the University of Oslo and at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in Trondheim. In 2003, a project group was initiated and the most important patents were achieved. A year later, 2004, the concept evolved to a general design and a 1:20 scale model was tested in a wave tank of the Ocean Basin Laboratory at the Sintef in Trondheim. It was tested in operational and extreme conditions. The tests confirmed the concept and the excellent properties of the structure in a sea environment. Following the positive outcome of the first tests, the construction of a research platform of about scale 1:3 (Figure 2), named 'Buldra', was also built and tested in the Ocean Basin Laboratory.

Figure 2 The Buldra research platform at about scale 1:3.

Buldra has dimensions of 12 square meters and is 9 meter high. The hydraulic towers on the platform are 7 meter high. The test device was designed with a total of five point absorbers (or buoys or 'eggs') a complete hydraulic system, a generator and an electrical load. A monitor system was also developed for the tests. The major objectives of these tests were to verify the system design, measure actual power production capability versus the theoretical calculations, identify and measure energy loss components and to give input to the control algorithms. The 1:3 scale system tests verified the production potential of the platform. The tests also verified the most important energy loss components and their relative importance in the power production system. After these basin tests, Buldra was ready for sea trials. It was launched in the

sea in January 2005 off the southern coast of Norway. This device is used for extensive monitoring and testing and gives important input to the development of the next generation plants.

Focus on the point absorbers

The focus is the design, producing and testing of the floating point absorbers which are made in filament wound glass/polyester composite. Within the Seewec project the shape has evolved: from egg to tulip, to pencil to short cone/cylinder/cone shape which is now the proposed one. The fibre winding angles, ply thicknesses and structural stiffness and strength have resulted from extensive finite element calculations within Abaqus, coupled with the filament winding geometry software Cadwind to obtain the local winding angles in every layer. Figure 3 shows both the proposed shape in the Cadwind environment (left) and in the Abaqus environment (right).

Figure 3 Cone/Cylinder/Cone point absorber in Cadwind (left) and Abaqus (right).

In state of extreme loads, slamming has been the reason for ship damage. Slamming is a phenomenon, known in the maritime environment, as the repeated short impact of water on a floating or sailing structure. The upward propelling of a structure and the fall back on the water surface, is called straight, vertical or bottom slamming. The phenomenon was already extensively studied in the field of navigation. The slamming of a breaking wave, called ‘breaking wave slamming’ or ‘lateral slamming’, occurs when a wave hits the structure at a certain moment in its breaking phase. Both sorts of slamming are shown schematically on the buoys in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Schematic view of bottom slamming (left) and breaking wave slamming (right) [1-3].

Brevik, one of the partners in the Seewec project, performed measurements at Karmøy to determine the sea climate [4]. The return level of n years means a storm that occurs once in n years. The return level of 25 years (with a significant wave height H_s of 9.6 m and a significant wave period of T_s 9.9 s) is seen within the project as an extreme state which the point absorbers should survive. Considering the 25-year storm within the sea climate at the Norwegian coast, lateral slamming (wave impact with localized peak pressures) on these buoys is the most critical loading condition. All slamming calculations are done with a constant pressure according to Det Norske Veritas (DNV)[5].

INFLUENCE OF DEFORMABLE STRUCTURES

Test samples: rigid and hollow cylinder

As the buoys clearly deform under the extreme slamming pressures, they cannot be considered as a rigid structure, which will affect the peak pressures. To investigate this phenomenon, laboratory scale slamming tests on both a rigid and deformable cylinder have been performed and compared with CFD calculations in the code Fluent using the Volume of Fluid model (VOF). First, two cylinders were made on a laboratory scale winding machine. They have a diameter of 300 mm and a length of 400 mm. The rigid one is a full cylinder as is shown in Figure 5 on the left and the deformable one is hollow as is shown on the right of the same figure [2, 3, 6].

Figure 5 Picture of the full cylinder (left) and the hollow one (right) [2, 3, 6].

Slamming set-up

The slamming set-up had to fulfil several design conditions. It should be able to simulate both straight and lateral slamming. In other words structures can fall down from different sides to the water. Next, it is more useful if the set-up can be used for several shapes besides the 'egg'. Finally, the possibility of simulating repeated slamming should be taken into consideration. Of course, the location is also important. Since there was one location available with a large well in the ground the design is based with this boundary condition in mind. Figure 6 shows a picture of the final design with the hollow cylinder ready for testing [1-3, 7, 8].

Figure 6 Picture of the slamming set-up with the hollow cylinder on it, ready for testing [1-3, 7, 8].

This set-up was achieved with the help of T. Derveaux, W. Baro, J. Himpe and D. Van Nuffel with work done for their master theses [1-3, 7, 8]. The full cylinder was foreseen of a pressure sensor and two strain gauges. The strain gauges are fixed with M-Bond 200. Both strain gauges, a perpendicular and longitudinal one, are located next to the pressure sensor as is shown in Figure 7. For the hollow cylinder the instrumentation was mounted on exactly the same location. However, two additional strain gauges were mounted on the inner side of the object at the same location as the outer ones.

Figure 7 Full cylinder with instrumentation: 2 strain gauges and a pressure sensor.

Experimental and numerical results

The experiments with the full cylinder were done six times with the pressure sensor down (called 0 degrees) from a drop height of 1000 mm. This equals a drop velocity of about 4.43 m/s. A representative pressure signal for the drop tests at 0 degrees is shown

in Figure 8. The peak pressure is about 730 kPa which equals a C_p of about 75. In literature Lin and Shieh (1997) calculated this dimensionless pressure coefficient C_p out of experiments. Their main findings are shown in Figure 9 [9]. The dimensionless pressure coefficient at zero degrees, $C_p(0)$, peaks at about 110 to 120. This is a safe estimation instead of the infinite C_p according to the Wagner model. The maximum peak pressure for a drop velocity of 4.43 m/s corresponding with this C_p is 1080 kPa to 1177 kPa which is higher than the measured value for the full cylinder. In these experiments the full cylinder is considered as rigid but of course this is not entirely true. Additionally, in Lin and Shieh also different C_p values were found but 110-120 was proposed as a safe value.

Figure 8 Pressure signal for the full cylinder at zero degrees; drop height 1000 mm [2, 3, 7].

Figure 9 Dimensionless pressure coefficient proposed by Lin and Shieh [9].

The tests on the hollow cylinder measured the pressure again at zero degrees. Six of these tests were done. In the measured signals it became clear that the pressure peak was a lot lower for the deformable cylinder than for the rigid cylinder. The average is 335 kPa which is almost a factor two smaller. A representative curve is given in Figure 10. This result is in good agreement with CFD calculations in Fluent as is shown later on in

this section. Further experiments will be done under 30 degrees again to validate the experiments with Lin and Shieh and to assess the (expected decreasing) difference between deformable and rigid structures.

Figure 10 Pressure signal for the hollow cylinder zero degrees; drop height 1000 mm [2, 3, 7]

The impact of an object on a water surface is a fluid structure interaction problem. Until now this has not been considered within this paper. However, the hydrodynamic pressures that occur at water entry of the body, lead to deformations of that body. Additionally, these deformations influence the pressures. The pressures, calculated with Fluent should be given as a boundary condition to Abaqus and the deformation of the structure, calculated in the latter, should be given as a boundary condition to Fluent. Since it is not straight forward to exchange information between the two programs, a coupling-algorithm was used as proposed by Vierendeels et al [10]. For validation purposes, the same geometry as the hollow cylinder is chosen. The influence of the deformation on the peak pressures was researched. This was done by comparing four different test cases: first, an uncoupled calculation with a constant velocity of the cylinder; second, an uncoupled calculation with 6 degrees of freedom (DOF) which determines the displacement of the cylinder by the working forces on it and by its inertia; third, a coupled calculation of the cylinder with the non-rigid elastic properties of the composite; and finally, a coupled calculation with an elastic isotropic material with a very high E-modulus to simulate a rigid cylinder. All calculations were done with 400 elements on the half cylinder and a time step of 10 μ s. The different dimensionless pressure (C_p) signals are given in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Comparison of the dimensionless pressure coefficient in time during coupled, uncoupled, rigid and deformable calculations [6, 11].

The coupled calculation of the rigid cylinder matches very well with the uncoupled calculation of the 6 DOF model which shows that the coupling works fine. These two calculations use the same boundary condition but a different solution model. However, the mesh and time step are not small enough to capture the peak pressures. The peak pressure coefficient for the coupled composite calculation is quite a lot lower, 40-45 instead of 75-80 for the rigid one which is almost a factor two. This calculated value for the rigid cylinder matches very well with the earlier mentioned value of the experimental tests. For the experimental test case of the hollow cylinder this would mean a maximum pressure of 370-416 kPa (where the pressure is calculated out of the C_p equation) which is in good agreement with the measured value of 335 kPa. This difference between calculation and experiment could be caused by a theoretical constant velocity which, in reality, decreases.

LARGE SCALE EXPERIMENTS

Test samples: two point absorbers

In a last phase, two buoys have been manufactured on ‘Buldra’ scale, one sandwich structure and one monolithic structure. The first one is called the ‘Buoy With Foam’ (BWF) and the latter ‘Buoy Without Foam’ (BWO). In the first test, the egg is loaded in fatigue at the set-up in the laboratory Magnel of Ghent University. The buoy is loaded on its side, over a sector segment of 60 degrees. This test is an experimental simulation of repeated breaking wave slamming. A picture of the set up is given in Figure 12. The yearly storm at the location in Norway was considered to have a period of 6 seconds and a height of 6.6 meters, duration of 24 hours per year and the buoy should have a lifetime of 25 years. This results in an amount of 360000 cycles.

Figure 12 Picture of a buoy in the fatigue set up.

Next, two kinds of drop tests were carried out, namely one called the lateral (or breaking wave) and the straight (or bottom) slamming. This means that the buoy was dropped from different sides into the water. For the lateral slamming tests, the buoy was dropped at its side into the water as is shown in Figure 13 (left). Again, this sort of test resembles a breaking wave hitting the buoy on its side. The celerity for the ‘1 year storm’ ($H_s = 6.6$ m) is 9.75 m/s. The drop speed is considered to be equal to the celerity of a particular wave. Hence, the celerity of 9.75 m/s equals a drop height of about 4.85 m. Per buoy there were 10 such tests planned with the pressure sensors down and with those sensors over 30 degrees. For the straight tests the buoy was dropped ‘straight-up’ as is seen in Figure 13 (right). Also, forty bottom tests were done [12].

Figure 13 Picture of lateral (left) and straight slamming (right) drop test.

Figure 14 shows some pictures of the scene during tests. The crane is mounted on the shore which is shown on the upper left. The instrumentation for reading out the high speed camera, strain gauges, accelerometers and pressure sensors was mounted on the river shore as is shown at the upper right. On the lower left a picture is given after a drop test and the buoy is prepared to be lifted again. On the lower right picture the buoy rests still on solid ground and is prepared to be lifted over the water. The crane had to lift the egg in two different ways, straight and lateral. For both sort of tests two elastic cables were attached to the flanges on the edges of the buoy. A simple mechanical system allowed releasing the egg. The real drop height was 4.8 m since it was measured through an internal measuring system in the crane.

Figure 14 Pictures of the surroundings during experiments on the “Watersportbaan”.

Finally, as for the fatigue test, the buoy is again tested indoor on its side over a segment of 60 degrees to simulate breaking wave slamming. However, this time the purpose is the determination of the maximum load that the buoy can resist. The set-up is the same as for the fatigue test, but another load cell with a higher capacity (2000 kN) was used since the predicted failure load for the BWF (strongest buoy) was about 1320 kN. A building-up load program was applied. The first step was a load of 300 kN (equal to the load used for the fatigue test). Once it was stable, the load was increased up to 450 kN. Next step was 600 kN and from then on the load was augmented further in steps of 100 kN. Each load step lasted for ten minutes with one exception of at about 450 kN which lasted longer (about one hour) since that load could be considered equal to the 25 year storm which is calculated out of the DNV norm.

Experimental results

The location of each strain gauge is given in Figure 15. The dotted square in the left drawing is the location of the magnified right drawing. The peak strains in the signals of the fourteen strain gauges for the fatigue tests are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 15 The inner ‘Magnet’ strain gauges divided in three groups; measurements in mm.

There it is seen that some of the strain gauges measure higher strains than calculated and vice versa as expected since the simulations allow free deformations while the indoor fatigue tests limits this with the help of a rigid shell. Nevertheless the order of magnitude is in good agreement.

	BWF (experimental)	BWF (calculations)	BWOF (experimental)	BWOF (calculations)
ML0_1	700-1000	1500	800-1000	2500
MD0_1	800-1200	1700	1000	880
ML20_1	400-500	1000	800-1400	2100
MD20_1	800-1200	1300	600-1250	750
ML0_2	500	1500	1400-2000	2500
MD0_2	500	1700	400-900	880
ML20_2	700	1000	800-1200	2000
MD20_2	1500-2500	1500	750-1000	880
ML0_3	1200-2000	700	3200	450
MD0_3	1200	910	1000	610
ML20_3	500-2000	600	100-200	450
MD20_3	500	690	500-1750	610
ML0_4	1200-1500	700	250	450
MD0_4	2000	910	900-1000	600

Table 1 Summarised results in microstrain of strain gauges during fatigue test in microstrain.

For the lateral drop tests three pressure signals (A23C, A06 and A07) and a shock accelerometer were measured. A representative measurement of the shock accelerometer for an experiment at a drop height of 4.8 m is given in Figure 16. Out of this signal the velocity at impact is determined. Again, a representative graph of the velocity for the same drop height is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 16 Signal of the shock accelerometer during impact of the buoy for a drop test at 4.8 m in a lateral manner.

The theoretical drop speed at 4.8 m is 9.7 m/s. An average of the experimental impact speed was made for all (forty) breaking wave test at a drop height of 4.8 m. This average is 9.33 m/s. Also, the standard deviation was calculated and is 0.5 m/s. The high speed camera was used to register the events with high accuracy and another means of determining the drop speed. Results are quite similar with those of the shock accelerometer since the average for the drop tests of 4.8 m is 9.6 m/s and the standard deviation 0.19 m/s.

Figure 17 Integrated signal of the accelerometer; velocity at impact of the buoy for a drop test at 4.8 m in a lateral manner.

For the zero degrees tests the shock pressure sensor A06 and the A07 were useful. In the preparation phase it was assumed to have some results out of the A23C as well for the 30 degrees tests. However, for the zero degrees tests this sensor is not taken into account. The results of the A06 and A07 for the BWOFF at zero degrees are shown in Figure 18. The sensor A06 gives a peak pressure equal to about 1.8 MPa. The average value is 2.23 MPa with a standard deviation of 0.46 MPa.

Figure 18 Pressure sensors A06 and A07 signals for BWOFF when dropped at zero degrees.

The A07 peak takes place a bit later and is also a lot smaller, which is consistent with their respective location on the buoy as is shown in Figure 19. This average value is 0.2 MPa with a standard deviation of 0.03 MPa. Next, a representative graph for one of the BWF tests at zero degrees is given in Figure 20. There, the average value of the A06 sensor is 3.5 MPa with a standard deviation of 0.14 MPa. For the BWF A07 its average is 0.21 MPa with a standard deviation of 0.07 MPa. Also tests were done at 30 degrees. The average for these tests is 0.31 MPa for the BWF and 0.305 MPa for the BWOFF with respective standard deviations of 0.05 MPa and 0.06 MPa. Here, also the A23C sensor

was measured. The average peak pressure for the BWF is 0.34 MPa and for the BWOFF 0.31 MPa with respective standard deviation of 0.03 MPa and 0.02 MPa. The pressure coefficient, C_p , for 0 degrees and 30 degrees is respectively 110 – 120 and 7.5 (Lin & Shieh). For the large scale lateral tests this would mean that $P(0^\circ)$ equals 4.79 – 5.22 MPa (calculated with the experimental average velocity of 9.33 m/s) and $P(30^\circ)$ equals 0.32 MPa. Now, the average measured values give a quite good agreement since these are 3.50 MPa for the BWF_P (0°) and 0.31 MPa for the P (30°). For the BWOFF_P (0°) a lower maximum pressure is measured of 2.23 MPa and for the BWOFF_P (30°) the average value is about the same as for the BWF, namely 0.305 MPa. The buoys are not 100% rigid, not even the BWF, so the difference between the experimental value of 3.5 MPa and 4.79 – 5.22 MPa seems quite reasonable. The drop tests were useful for gaining more knowledge about deformable behaviour under slamming conditions.

Figure 19 Technical drawing of the location of the pressure sensors; note A23C, A06 and P07.

Figure 20 Pressure sensors P06 and P07 signals for BWF when dropped at zero degrees.

Within the static test until failure, the BWOFF has broken as soon as it reached 100 ton, the buoy with foam at 130 ton. Both values match very well with the calculated FEA simulations where the measure for Tsai Wu reaches one (i.e. failure) at 880 kN (BWOFF) and 1320 kN (BWF). Also, it has to be stated that fracture occurs very gradually which is a good thing. This means that at sea when one buoy breaks the whole structure can stay operational without any damage to the other parts. Some pictures of fracture are shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21 Buoy at fracture.

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